

Role of Patelloplasty in Relieving Anterior Knee Pain and Improve Patellar Tracking in Total Knee ArthroplastySandeep Chauhan¹, Sahil Mansotra², Maninder Singh Sahni³, Arnav Sharma⁴¹Senior Consultant, Department of Orthopedics, Artemis Hospital, Gurgaon²Fellow Arthroplasty, Department of Orthopedics, Artemis Hospital, Gurgaon³Senior Resident, Department of Orthopedics, Holy Family hospital, New Delhi⁴Resident Doctor, Department of Orthopedics, Artemis Hospital, Gurgaon

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Abstract:**Background:** Addressing anterior knee pain post-total knee arthroplasty (TKA) remains a significant concern. This study aims to present early outcomes of employing patelloplasty to alleviate such pain in TKA patients.**Methods:** A prospective review was conducted on 38 knees from 35 patients who underwent TKA between 2018 and 2022. Knee and function scores according to the Knee Society assessment, patellar scores using Feller's questionnaire, knee range of motion, and patient satisfaction were evaluated preoperatively and postoperatively.**Results:** Preoperative and final follow-up knee scores averaged 50.2±9.1 and 85.4±10.1, respectively, while function scores averaged 47.3±11.2 and 80.7±13.1, respectively. Preoperative patellar score averaged 17.9±3.2, increasing to 24.6±2.7 at final follow-up. Notably, knees with Grade 3 chondropathy exhibited significantly higher mean patellar scores compared to Grade 4 chondropathy knees. Preoperative knee range of motion averaged 82.7±11.5, improving to 115.2±8.9 at final follow-up.**Conclusion:** Employing patellar decompression with patelloplasty in TKA presents a viable option for alleviating anterior knee pain.**Keywords:** Patelloplasty, TKA, Pain, Knee.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Total knee arthroplasty (TKA) stands as one of the most effective interventions for debilitating knee conditions, providing substantial relief and functional improvement for millions worldwide. However, despite advancements in surgical techniques and implant design, anterior knee pain (AKP) remains a common postoperative complication, often stemming from patellar maltracking and associated disorders.

Anterior knee pain remains a significant issue following total knee arthroplasty (TKA), affecting a wide range of patients (4–49%). [1] Its primary cause is often related to the patellofemoral joint, yet there's no consensus on its exact origins or the most effective treatment. This type of pain significantly contributes to patient dissatisfaction and post-TKR morbidity.

In recent years, the role of patelloplasty, a surgical technique involving reshaping and realignment of the patella, has garnered increasing attention as a means to address AKP and optimize patellar tracking following TKA. By addressing patellar malalignment, patelloplasty aims not only to

mitigate postoperative pain but also to enhance knee joint function and longevity of the prosthetic implant. The patellofemoral joint plays a pivotal role in knee biomechanics, and aberrations in its function can significantly impede the success of TKA.

Many aspects of anterior knee pain post-TKA still elude complete comprehension. The use of patellar resurfacing to alleviate this pain is contentious due to associated risks such as patellar fracture, subluxation, dislocation, aseptic loosening, and necrosis. [2]

Traditionally, treatment has involved patelloplasty, which includes the removal of osteophytes and electrocautery-based denervation of the patella. Our study aimed to compare the efficacy of patelloplasty in TKA with and without patellar denervation using electrocautery, assessing anterior knee pain and clinical outcomes over a two-year period. The decision to perform patellar resurfacing during total knee arthroplasty (TKA) hinges significantly on understanding the causes of postoperative anterior knee pain, particularly those stemming from patellofemoral joint pathology. [3-6] This pain can

arise from various factors, including increased venous engorgement within the patella, abnormal patellofemoral rhythm and pressure, and elevated subchondral bone pressure, all of which have been associated with pain generation. Drilling through the subchondral bone of the patella has been shown to alleviate intraosseous pressure, thereby reducing pain and potentially improving patellar cartilage health. Despite its potential benefits, the role of patelloplasty in TKA remains a topic of debate among orthopedic surgeons. While some studies advocate for its routine incorporation into surgical protocols, others question its efficacy and necessity, emphasizing the need for further investigation and evidence-based guidelines.

The primary aim of this study was to assess the clinical outcomes and patient satisfaction associated with patelloplasty. By evaluating these outcomes, the study aimed to provide insights into the efficacy of this approach in reducing anterior knee pain and improving postoperative satisfaction in TKA patients.

Methods

This prospective study involved 38 knees from 35 patients (22 females and 13 males, with a mean age of 66.8 years, ranging from 58 to 84 years) who underwent total knee arthroplasty (TKA) for Grade 4 knee osteoarthritis between January 2018 and December 2022. Of these, 32 patients had unilateral TKA. Each participant underwent primary TKA using the same surgical approach and implants. The exclusion criteria, based on Barrack et al., included previous tibial osteotomy, surgeries involving the extensor mechanism, a history of septic arthritis or osteomyelitis, severe medical conditions limiting mobility, disabling diseases affecting other lower extremity joints, inflammatory arthropathy, or significant deformity (varus or valgus angulation, or flexion contracture over 15 degrees). Anteroposterior radiographs of the hip, knee, and ankle were assessed preoperatively, postoperatively, and at the final follow-up, along with additional knee, lateral, and axial (sunrise) radiographs. All patients provided written informed consent, and the local ethics committee approved the use of medical records and the re-evaluation of patients.

All surgeries were performed by the same surgeon. All patients followed a standardized perioperative regimen, including antibiotic administration before tourniquet inflation and venous thrombosis prophylaxis, with antibiotics continued until drain removal. The procedures used a consistent medial parapatellar approach and technique with Genesis II, a posterior stabilized fixed bearing prosthesis. Cement was used to insert the femoral and tibial components. The need for lateral retinacular release was determined by patellar tracking using the "no thumb" technique. Intraoperatively, the patella was

everted and examined for chondromalacia, graded according to the Outerbridge classification: Grade 1 (softening and swelling), Grade 2 (partial-thickness defect), Grade 3 (fissuring to subchondral bone), and Grade 4 (exposed subchondral bone). [7] 11 patellae had Grade 4 injuries, while 27 had Grade 3 chondromalacia.

Patelloplasty was performed on all patients, involving cauterization of the patellar rim for peripheral denervation and osteophyte removal for better patella seating on the femoral component's trochlea. Clinical and radiographic evaluations were conducted at 3, 6, and 12 months postoperatively. The Knee Society criteria were used to assess knee and function scores before surgery and at the final follow-up. Additionally, a patellofemoral pain questionnaire by Feller et al. was administered before surgery and at the final follow-up, covering anterior knee pain, quadriceps strength, chair rise ability, and stair climbing ability. Range of motion (ROM) was evaluated preoperatively and postoperatively. Levitsky et al.'s patient satisfaction questionnaire was completed during the last follow-up exams. For statistical analysis, preoperative and final follow-up results were used, conducted with SPSS 126 (SPSS for Windows 26, Chicago, IL, USA). The paired samples t-test compared preoperative and postoperative values of the Knee Society Clinical Rating System (knee and function scores), patellar score, and knee ROM. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. The correlation between postoperative patellar scores, knee and function scores, and ROM was assessed using Pearson's correlation test.

Results

The mean follow-up duration was 38.4 months (range: 22 to 65 months). One patient experienced an acute infection, necessitating a revision surgery in the second month, which was classified as a failure. Postoperative clinical and radiographic evaluations indicated no signs of instability or loosening. Additionally, no patellar fractures, dislocations, or symptomatic subluxations were detected.

The mean knee score improved significantly from 50.2 ± 9.1 preoperatively to 85.4 ± 10.1 postoperatively ($p < 0.001$). The mean knee range of motion (ROM) also showed significant improvement, increasing from 82.7 ± 11.5 preoperatively to 115.2 ± 8.9 postoperatively, a gain of 32.5° ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, the knee function score increased from 47.3 ± 11.2 to 80.7 ± 13.1 ($p < 0.001$). The preoperative patellar score of 17.9 ± 3.2 rose to a postoperative score of 24.6 ± 2.7 , which was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), reflecting an increase of 6.7 points.

According to the Knee Society criteria, 36 knees (94.7%) were rated as excellent or good postoperatively.

The patient satisfaction questionnaire indicated that 26 knees (68.4%) were "extremely" and 9 (23.6%) were "very" satisfied, two knees (5.3%) were somewhat satisfied, and one knee (2.6%) was somewhat dissatisfied with the surgical outcomes. The postoperative patellar score showed a positive correlation with the postoperative knee score

($r=0.82$, $p<0.001$), postoperative function score ($r=0.83$, $p<0.001$), and ROM ($r=0.61$, $p<0.001$). Analyzing the degree of damage based on patellar cartilage scores, knees with Grade 3 chondropathy had a patella score of 25.8 ± 2.3 , while knees with Grade 4 chondropathy had a score of 23.5 ± 3.0 .

The difference between Grade 3 and Grade 4 knees was statistically significant ($p=0.01$). Three knees (7.9%) experienced anterior knee pain, all of which had Grade 4 chondropathy.

Table 1: Preoperative and postoperative values of the knees

Variable	Preoperative		Postoperative		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Knee score	50.2	9.1	85.4	10.1	<0.001
Range of Motion	82.7	11.5	115.2	8.9	<0.001
Function Score	47.3	11.2	80.7	13.1	<0.001
Patellar score	17.9	3.2	24.6	2.7	<0.001

Table 2: Patient satisfaction

Questionnaire response	Number (%)
Extremely satisfied	26 (68.4%)
Very satisfied	9 (23.6%)
Somewhat satisfied	2 (5.3%)
Neutral	0
Somewhat dissatisfied	1 (2.6%)
Extremely dissatisfied	0

Figure 1: Correlation between postoperative Patellar Score and Knee Score, Function Score, ROM

Figure 2:

Figure 3:

Discussion

The pathophysiology of anterior knee pain in osteoarthritis is often complex, involving factors such as erosion of the patellar cartilage and surface irregularities, which contribute to pain in many patients. Studies indicate that increased pressure within the bone can lead to deep aching pain, particularly at rest, in some individuals with osteoarthritis of the hip and knee. [8-11] Elevated pressure within the bone, caused by factors like venous stasis, can result in periosteal deformation

and new bone growth, leading to various types of bone-related pain. Surgical procedures such as drilling the subchondral bone or performing patelloplasty have been utilized to alleviate pain in osteoarthritic patients. [12,13]

In our investigation, we observed significant enhancements in various parameters including total knee scores, function scores, patellar scores, knee range of motion (ROM), and patient satisfaction assessments from preoperative to final follow-up evaluations. Our outcomes according to the Knee

Society Knee and Function Scores aligned closely with figures documented in existing literature. [14] Utilizing the Genesis II PS prosthesis, which offers a maximum range of motion of 135°, our operative procedures yielded results indicating no substantial disparity in mean preoperative versus postoperative knee scores and functional scores, irrespective of whether patellar resurfacing was conducted during total knee arthroplasty (TKA). Levitsky et al. [5], in a study spanning a mean follow-up duration of 7.5 years, reported a notable patient satisfaction rate of 89.5% following TKA without patellar resurfacing. However, findings from various randomized controlled clinical trials indicate a significantly higher incidence of postoperative anterior knee pain in groups where patellar resurfacing was not performed. [15-17] conversely, some trials have shown no marked difference in the occurrence of postoperative anterior knee pain between cases with or without patellar resurfacing during TKA procedures.

Burnett et al. [14] highlighted that anterior knee pain persisted in 50% of cases with preoperative patellar pain, even after patellar resurfacing, with no alleviation observed even at the 10-year follow-up mark. In our study, postoperative anterior knee pain was detected in 8.2% of knees, all of which exhibited Grade 4 chondropathy. Additionally, patellar scores from knees with Grade 3 chondropathy surpassed those with Grade 4 chondropathy.

Thus, considering these findings, patellar resurfacing may be deemed more suitable for knees afflicted with Grade 4 chondropathy. Anterior knee pain contributes significantly to the patellar scoring system, alongside criteria such as quadriceps strength and functional abilities. Our study showed a significant increase in patellar scores following patelloplasty with decompression, indicating potential benefits for certain patients. Although our study had limitations, including its non-comparative design and short follow-up period, it underscores the need for prospective, randomized trials to better understand the efficacy of different surgical approaches in managing anterior knee pain.

Conclusion

Patellar resurfacing could be considered a superior choice for knees affected by Grade 4 chondropathy. On the other hand, patellar decompression didn't elevate the patellar score in knees with Grade 3 chondropathy, and we didn't find significant evidence of improvement in this regard. Nonetheless, considering the potential challenges associated with patellar revision surgeries, conducting more comprehensive studies to explore the reduction of intraosseous pressure in the patella would be beneficial.

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